

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of Alcohols*

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Raney nickel (W-6) and Adkins copper chromite catalyst may be used to effect dehydrogenation of octan-2-ol and decahydroanacardol to the corresponding ketones. The method is simple and the yields are superior in comparison with the usual oxidation methods.

CATALYTIC dehydrogenation of alcohols is a useful method for the preparation of aldehydes from primary alcohols and ketones from secondary alcohols¹ and is often preferable to usual oxidation methods, when larger quantities are involved.

Copper chromite is known as dehydrogenation catalyst². The predominant process occurring when alcohols decompose on metallic catalysts is usually dehydrogenation.

The dehydrogenation of alcohols is an endothermic process and hence the position of equilibrium is progressively shifted to the aldehyde or ketone side as the temperature is raised. With copper chromite as the dehydrogenation catalyst, a number of secondary alcohols have been dehydrogenated in the liquid phase³. In some of these dehydrogenations, special degassed Raney catalyst and cyclohexanone as a hydrogen acceptor have also been used⁴.

The object of the present investigation was to standardise the catalytic dehydrogenation of octan-2-ol to octan-2-one in the liquid phase and at the same time compare the catalytic activity of Adkin's copper chromite and various Raney metal catalysts. The optimum conditions so established were employed for the dehydrogenation of decahydroanacardol.

The varieties of Raney metals used for the dehydrogenation studies are summarised in Table 1. In these experiments, the use of any hydrogen acceptor is avoided. Moreover, copper chromite and Raney metals prepared in the ordinary way have been employed in all the experiments. The rate of dehydrogenation by various catalysts was studied by actual collection of hydrogen liberated. The percentage yield of ketone formed in each batch was obtained by analysis.

Experimental

1) *Preparation of Raney nickel*: Raney nickel was prepared by the method of Adkins and Billica³ and after exhaustive washing, the catalyst was stored under absolute alcohol.

2) *Preparation of Raney copper*: Raney copper was obtained by the action of NaOH solution (30%) on Dewarda alloy (Al, 50%; Cu, 45%; Zn, 5%) and then processed and stored as Raney nickel.

3) *Preparation of Raney cobalt*: Raney cobalt was prepared by the method of Aller⁴. The cobalt aluminium alloy (200-300 mesh) was first prepared and then digested in a solution of NaOH (30%). The catalyst was prepared and stored as Raney nickel.

TABLE 1—DEHYDROGENATION OF OCTAN-2-OL, USING DIFFERENT CATALYSTS.

Expt. No.	Octan-2-ol in gms	Type of catalysts used	Catalyst concentration in gms	Temp. of the oil bath 0°	Total evolution of hydrogen mls	Total yield of the product in gms	Ketone conversion %	Reaction period Hrs/Min.
1.	10 gms for each experiment	R-Co	0.5 g for each experiment	197-98	No effect	Catalyst rejected		
2.		R-Cu		182-92	1172	8.6	47.10	10.00
3.		Recovered R-Cu reused		197-98	1247	8.7	47.11	10.30
4.		R-Ni		197-98	2347	9.8	98.7	5.00
5.		Recovered R-Ni reused		197-98	2170	9.6	96.0	5.00
6.		Recovered R-Ni reused second time		198-200	2022	8.7	87.56	5.30
7.		Cu-chromite		197-98	2284	9.9	99.00	4.00
8.		Recovered Cu-chromite reused		197-98	1961	8.9	96.37	4.15
9.		Recovered Cu-chromite reused second time		198-200	1854	8.7	93.94	5.00
10.		Recovered Cu-chromite reused third time		197-99	1775	8.7	91.3	5.00

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4) *Preparation of copper chromite catalyst*: The copper chromite catalyst was prepared by the modified procedure of Lazier and Arnold⁶. The crude catalyst obtained was stored in a bottle.

5) *Typical dehydrogenation procedure*: Octan-2-ol (10 g), Raney catalyst (0.5 g) were refluxed without stirring till the evolution of hydrogen was complete, (as shown by ceasing of displacement of water from a Winchester jar). The catalyst was filtered and Octan-2-one obtained was distilled. The percentage concentration of ketone in the distillate was estimated by adopting hydroxyl amine hydrochloride procedure⁶; using bromophenol blue as the indicator.

6) *Dehydrogenation of Decahydroanacardol*: Decahydroanacardol (2 g) was dehydrogenated over Raney nickel (2 g) at 162°–63° for fifteen minutes. There was a brisk evolution of hydrogen. When the evolution of hydrogen was complete, the reaction was stopped. The substituted cyclohexanone derivative (wt. 1.8 g; yield: 90%), so obtained was once crystallised from n-hexane (m. p. 45°–46°; Found: C, 81.63; H, 13.14%. $C_{21}H_{40}O$ requires C, 81.75; H, 13.07%). This was identified as decahydroanacardol from its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, crystallised from acetic acid (m. p. 134°–35°, Found: N, 11.2%; $C_{27}H_{44}N_4O_4$ requires N, 11.47%).

7) *Oxidation of Decahydroanacardol*: Decahydroanacardol (2g) was oxidised by the Oppenauer oxidation method. The secondary alcoholic group was oxidised to ketone. The substituted cyclohexanone derivative (wt. 1.2 g; yield: 60%) so obtained was recrystallised from n-hexane (m. p. 45°–46°, Found: C, 81.68; H, 13.12%; $C_{21}H_{40}O$ requires C, 81.75; H, 13.07%). The 2:4 dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m. p. 133°–35° on analysis, gave N, 11.18%. $C_{27}H_{44}N_4O_4$ requires N, 11.47%. The mixed melting point of the two ketones obtained as above was undepressed (m. p. 134°–35°).

Results and Discussion

Raney nickel (W 6) and Adkins copper chromite catalyst proved to be good dehydrogenation catalysts at the reflux temp. of 2-octanol. The yields of 2-octanone were almost quantitative. The catalysts did not show much deactivation on repeated use. Under the same conditions copper was less effective than nickel and cobalt showed no activity. Unlike copper chromite catalyst, the dehydrogenation starts instantaneously at the boiling point of 2-octanol in case of Raney nickel.

In the case of dehydrogenation of decahydroanacardol with Raney nickel (W-6) at the reflux temperature 162°–63°, it was observed that the reaction is usually too fast and after the completion of the first reaction, the secondary reaction starts, if the dehydrogenation is prolonged, giving rise to pentadecyl cyclohexane.

A plot of hydrogen collected in cubic centimeters against time in hours for the dehydrogenation of 2-octanol is shown in Fig. 1. The graph shows that the evolution of hydrogen is very brisk in the first hour but rapidly falls down in the next hour.

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Fig. 1. Dehydrogenation of Octan-2-OL over Metal Catalysts

